

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL LOLLIPOP FOR COUGH TREATMENT AND IMMUNITY ENHANCEMENT

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Abstract

Formulation and evaluation of polyherballollipops was undertaken to provide an alternative treatment and dosage form for managing cough particularly in paediatric patients and to improve patient compliance by offering a palatable and easy-to-administer dosage form. Cough is a prevalent medical complaint, and lollipops offer an attractive solution, especially for children who have difficulty in swallowing traditional solid or liquid dosage forms. The lollipops were prepared using heating and congealing technique, incorporating different herb extracts including Tulsi, Ashwagandha, Musk melon seeds, Amla, Honey, Jaggery, Corn syrup etc. into a sucrose based matrix. The prepared lollipops were evaluated for organoleptic properties, thickness, hardness, friability, weight variation, moisture content, mouth dissolving time, stability and antimicrobial activity. The results demonstrated the successful formulation of polyherbal lollipop with satisfactory comprehensive evaluations, physical parameters, stability over different storage conditions and antimicrobial effectiveness.

Keywords

Herbal, lollipops, cough, paediatrics

INTRODUCTION

Cough is a reflex action that serves as a protective mechanism for the respiratory system, is a common and often underestimated symptom. It can be caused by various factors, ranging from respiratory infections to environmental irritants. One of the most frequent medical complaints (cough) represents up to 30 million clinical visits annually. A referral to a pulmonologist occurs in as many as 40% of these problems. Coughing is a natural, instinctive response that aids the body's immune system in defending against invaders. Numerous clinical correlations and etiologies have been linked to coughing. Moreover, there are no therapeutically useful instruments for measuring or quantifying coughs objectively. [13] The cough is a natural defense mechanism that can successfully protect the respiratory system from foreign body inhalation and by removing excessive bronchial secretions when combined with phagocytosis, bronchoconstriction, and mucociliary clearance. [8] Coughing can be triggered by non-infectious causes such as smoke, dust, and pet dander, or by infectious agents like bacteria and viruses. It also helps expel food or foreign objects that accidentally enter the airway. Coughing can be both voluntary and involuntary. When nerve endings in airways are irritated by environmental factors like pollen or dust, the cough reflex activates to expel the irritant. A cough may also develop from a viral infection, helping your lungs clear mucus accumulated as part of the immune response.

TYPES OF COUGH

Fig.1: Types of cough

Mechanism of cough [13]

Fig.2: Mechanism of action of cough

Each cough occurs through the stimulation of a complex reflex arc. This is initiated by the irritation of cough receptors which are found in the trachea, main carina, branching points of large airways, and more distal smaller airways; also, they are present in the pharynx. The most common cause of chronic dry cough is a group of related conditions of chronic rhinitis, sinusitis, and postnasal drip. In these cases the cough reflex may be sensitized through an action of inflammatory mediators from the nasal mucosa on the airways or a reflex sensitization of airway sensory nerves.

Immunity

The human immune system, a complex network of cells, tissues, and organs, stands as the body's formidable defense against pathogens and foreign invaders. Understanding the intricacies of human immunity is paramount in appreciating how our bodies protect themselves and maintain health.

Fig.3: Types of immunity

LOLLIPOPS

The administration of drugs through oral route is the most common and the easiest way of administering a drug. The oral route of drug administration is widely accepted, accounting for 50-60% of all dosage forms. Solid dosage form provides ease of administration, accurate dosage, self-medication, pain avoidance and most importantly the patient compliance. However, pediatrics, geriatric and bedridden patient shows inconvenience swallowing conventional tablets or capsules due to difficulties in swallowing with lesser amount of water, also unable to tolerate the taste of many drug when formulated as liquid dosage form, resulting in poor patient compliance. [23, 55] For the past two decades, there has been an enhanced demands for more patient friendly dosage form. Since the development cost of a new chemical entity is very high, the pharmaceutical companies are now focusing on the development of new drug delivery system for existing drug with an improved efficacy and bioavailability together with reduced dosing frequency to minimize side effects. [13, 23, 24] Lollipops are the flavoured medicated dosage form intended to be sucked

and held in mouth or pharynx containing one or more medicaments usually in the sweetened base. Lollipops are intended to relieve oropharyngeal symptoms, which are commonly caused by local infections and also for systemic effect provided the drug is well absorbed through the buccal linings or when it is swallowed. Lollipops are used for patients who cannot swallow solid oral dosage forms and for medications designed to be released slowly, providing a constant level of the drug in the oral cavity or coating the throat tissues with a solution of the drug. Drug often incorporated into lollipops include analgesics, anesthetics, antimicrobials, antiseptics. More amount of the drug will be absorbed from the buccal cavity and less will be swallowed and lost in GI tract. Lollipops can be given to children's or elderly patients improve patients compliance. However, this is by no means an exhaustive list as many other drugs may lend themselves to delivery by lollipops. [25]

Types of Lollipop

Hard Lollipop [25]

Hard lollipops can be considered solid syrups made from sugar. These dosage forms are created by heating sugars and other ingredients together and then pouring the mixture into a mold. They are similar to hard candy, and many hard lollipop formulas are modifications of hard candy recipes. The preparation requires low moisture content, so water is evaporated by boiling the sugar mixture during the process. Hard candy lollipops consist of sugar and other carbohydrates in an amorphous glassy state and typically have a moisture content of 0.5%-1.5%. Hard lollipops should not disintegrate but instead provide a slow, uniform dissolution over approximately 30 minutes.

Soft Lollipop[25]

Soft lollipops have gained popularity due to their ease of extemporaneous preparation and their suitability for a wide variety of drugs. The base typically consists of a mixture of various PEGs, acacia, glycerol, gelatin, and an acacia-sucrose base. These lollipops can be colored and flavored and may be either slowly dissolved in the mouth or chewed, depending on the intended effect of the incorporated drug.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials required were procured from different sources. Tulsi Powder (Antitussive, anti-inflammatory, Antibacterial), Ashwagandha extract (Immunity booster) and Amla Extract (Immunity booster) were procured from Sunpure Extracts pvt. Ltd. Ghaziabad (U.P). Muskmelon

Seeds (Antitussive, Antioxidant) and Jaggery(Sweetening agent) obtained from Local market ,Nanded, Maharashtra. Honey (Expectorant, Viscosity modifier) procured from Dabur India Ltd. Sucrose (Sweetening agent), Citric acid (Preservative) and HPMC procured from S D fine Chem-limited. Corn syrup (binder) obtained from Bexterpvt.Ltd., Ahmedabad.

Antimicrobial activity of herbal extracts

The specified quantities of herbs and extracts as in table 1, were taken and mixed and dilution of 100 µg/ml in DMSO was prepared and was used to study antimicrobial activity against Bordetella pertussis, Streptococcus pyrogenes, StreptococcusPneumoniae, Haemophilus influenza and the effect is compared with standard antibiotic streptomycin. The antimicrobial test was performed using well diffusion method.

The inoculum of the microorganism was prepared from the bacterial cultures. 15 ml of nutrient agar (Himedia) medium was poured in clean sterilized petriplates and allowed to cool and solidify. 100µl of broth of bacterial strain was pipette out and spread over the medium evenly. Wells of 6mm in diameter were bored using a sterile cork borer. Solutions of the compounds (100µg/ml) were prepared in DMSO and 100µl of prepared test solutions and standard was added to the wells. The petriplates incubated at 37⁰ C for 24 hours.

Antibacterial activity was evaluated by measuring the diameters of the zone of inhibitions. All the determinations were performed in triplicates.

Preparation of medicated lollipops

Heating and Congealing Technique

Required quantity of Jaggery syrup was prepared by mixing Jaggery and water. Sucrose was dissolved in small quantity of water and heated it to 110⁰C till sucrose dissolves completely forming as clear viscous syrup. Then the sucrose syrup was poured intoJaggery syrup and heated to 160⁰C. Flavour was added between 120⁰C to 135⁰C then temperature were brought down to 90⁰C anddrug, polymer and other ingredients were added and mixed well. The prepared mixture was poured into the calibrated mould and were kept in freeze for 1-2 hr. Then prepared lollipops were wrapped in aluminiumfoil and stored in desiccators to prevent moisture uptake.

Table 1: Formulation of Polyherbal lollipops

Sr.No.	Composition (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1	Tulsi	50	50	50	50	50	50
2	Ashwagandha	30	30	30	30	30	30
3	Musk melon	40	40	40	40	40	40
4	Amla	40	40	40	40	40	40
5	Honey	50	50	50	50	50	50
6	Jaggery	4000	-	1000	3500	800	3000
7	Sucrose	-	3900	2500	200	3000	800
8	Corn syrup	600	700	1000	900	800	600
9	HPMC	100	100	200	100	100	200
10	Citric acid	70	70	70	70	70	70
11	Calcium carbonate	20	20	20	20	20	20
12	Menthol crystals	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.
13	Purified water	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.

Evaluation of medicated lollipops

Organoleptic characterization

The prepared lollipops were analysed for color, odour and taste. The colour of formulation was observed against white and black background. Odour and taste of the lollipops were tested with the help of volunteers.

Thickness and Diameter

Measurement of thickness and Diameter is important for size and content uniformity of lollipop. Thickness and diameter was measured using Vernier caliper.

Weight Variation

Lollipops were randomly selected and checked to ensure weight uniformity. Twenty lollipops were taken and weighed individually and average weight was taken and percent weight variation was calculated.

Hardness and Friability

The durability of against shipping damage or breakage during storage, transportation, and handling before use is determined by hardness. The hardness of lollipops was measured using Monsanto hardness tester, with results expressed in kg/cm². Roche Friabilator was employed for friability testing. Twenty accurately weighed lollipops were placed in the tumbling apparatus, which rotates at 25 rpm. After 4 minutes, the lollipops were reweighed to determine the percentage weight loss.

Moisture content

One lollipop from each formulation was weighed and crushed in a mortar. 1 g sample was then taken and placed in a desiccator for 24 hours. After this period, the sample was weighed again. The moisture content was determined by subtracting the final weight from the initial weight of the lollipop sample.

Mouth dissolving time

The mouth dissolving time was determined by in-house method. The time taken by lollipop to dissolve completely was determined by placing each lollipop in separate beaker containing 100ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 at 50 rpm using mechanical stirrer and time was noted at 37⁰C.

Optimization of batch

All batches were evaluated for above tests and the batch which shows better results was considered optimized batch and evaluated for further study.

Stability studies

Stability studies were conducted on selected formulation as per ICH guidelines to provide the evidence of quality of product varies with time under the influence of temperature, humidity and light. The prepared formulation were packed in air tight container and subjected to different temperature and humidity conditions i.e ., 8°C ± 2°C, Room temperature and 40°C ± 2°C. The samples were withdrawn at different time interval over a period of one month and evaluated for physical appearance, color and odour.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical Characterization of Extracts

The prepared extracts of Tulsi, Ashwagandha, Musk melon, and Amla were subjected to various chemical tests to identify the presence of different classes of compounds. Alkaloids were detected in Tulsi, Ashwagandha, and Musk melon through Mayer's Test, but not in Amla. Carbohydrates were present in all samples, confirmed by Molish's Test, though specific carbohydrate tests like Benedict's and Selwinoff's produced varied results. Only Amla showed the presence of reducing sugars and cardiac glycosides. Proteins were detected in Musk melon and Amla by Millon's and Biuret tests. Flavonoids were present in all except Musk melon, verified by Lead Acetate tests. Phytosterols were identified in Tulsi, Ashwagandha and Musk melon. Phenolic content was only observed in Amla. The diverse presence of these compounds may make these herbs therapeutically effective.

Antimicrobial study

Antimicrobial assay was performed by using well diffusion method (table 2).

Table 2: Antimicrobial effect of lollipop

Sr. No.	Bacterial Species	Standard ZI (mm)	Sample ZI (mm)
1	Bordetella pertussis	30	21
2	Streptococcus pyrogenes	30	20
3	SreptococcusPneumoniae	30	22
4	Haemophilusinfluenzae	30	24

The plant extracts exhibited varying degrees of zone of inhibition showing antimicrobial effect against bacterial species which are responsible for throat infections i.e., Bordetella pertussis (21 mm), Streptococcus pyrogenes (20 mm), Sreptococcus Pneumoniae (22 mm), Haemophilus influenza (24 mm) and the effect is compared with standard antibiotic streptomycin (30mm). The significant zones of inhibition of herbal formulation suggest its potential use as alternative or complementary medicine for the treatment of ailments like throat infection, cough etc.

Fig.4:Antimicrobial assay of *B. Pertussis* Fig.5:Antimicrobial assay of *S. pyrogenes*

Fig.6:Antimicrobial assay of *S. pneumoniae*

Fig.7:Antimicrobial assay of *H. Influezae*

EVALUATION OF HERBAL LOLLIPOP

The prepared herbal medicated lollipops were evaluated for different parameters

Organoleptic characterization

Organoleptic characterization of lollipop formulation is important for patient acceptance and compliance. The prepared lollipops were inspected visually for colour, clarity, presence of any particular materials and texture. All the batches F1 to F6 were found to be Brownish orange, little sticky Smooth, homogeneous, good acceptable texture and with no presence of any particular matter.

Thickness and diameter of herbal lollipop

Thickness and diameter of the prepared lollipop gives the indication of content uniformity and is measured by using Vernier caliper. The thickness was found to be 9.5 mm – 10 mm and diameter 23 mm – 24 mm.

Weight variation

The weight variation test performed using 20 lollipops. Average weight and the individual weight of the 20 lollipops taken using electronic weighing balance. The results were found to be acceptable as per IP.

Hardness and friability

The durability of lollipops against shipping damage or breakage during storage, transportation, and handling before use is governed by their hardness. The hardness of lollipops was measured using Monsanto hardness tester and found in the range of 10.10 – 11.20 kg/cm² and friability tested using Roche Friabilator and the percent weight loss was below 1%.

Moisture content

1g of the sample was weighed and placed in oven at 105 ± 5°C until a constant weight was achieved. The moisture content is determined by subtracting the final weight from the initial weight of the sample of lollipops. The moisture content of F1, F2, F3, F4, F5 and F6 was found to be 40, 34, 29, 25, 21 and 19 percent respectively.

Mouth dissolving time of lollipop

Mouth dissolving time of herbal medicated lollipop F1, F2, F3, F4, F5 and F6 was found to be 7.30, 8.15, 8.00, 7.50, 7.40, and 7.30 minutes respectively.

Stability Studies of lollipop

One month stability studies were carried out and all the lollipops found to be stable after exposure at 8°C, Room Temperature and 40°C. The lollipop samples were found to be brownish orange and little sticky, with no crystallization and no presence of particular materials during one month exposure to all the conditions.

Conclusion

From the present study it can be concluded that candy based medicated lollipop may be a ideal dosage forms for pediatric patients for immunity enhancement and effective management of pharyngitis, tonsils, swollen gum etc. with additional advantage of patient compliance, convenience and comfort for efficient treatment including low dose, immediate onset of action, reduced dosage regimen and economy.

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Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Ethical approval

As this study does not involve animal subjects, ethical approval was not required

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